

GENERAL CONCEPT OF PEDAGOGY AS A SCIENCE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7219611>

ELSEVIER

Mokhira Eshanova Yuldashbaevna

, a senior lecturer, Specialized Branch of Tashkent

State University of Law

mohiraladybird@gmail.com

Received: 14-10-2022

Accepted: 17-10-2022

Published: 22-10-2022

Abstract: The formation of pedagogy as a science, its generalization of various facts as a science, and its causal relationships were widely covered.

Keywords: pedagogy, education, training, science, culture, object, enlightenment.

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

There are three points of view in the views of scientists on pedagogy:

Pedagogy is an interdisciplinary field of human knowledge. This approach actually denies pedagogy as an independent theoretical discipline, that is, as a field of reflection of pedagogical phenomena. In this case, the most diverse complex objects of reality (space, culture, politics, etc.) are manifested in pedagogy;

The use of practical disciplinary knowledge mediated by the pedagogic function is taken from other disciplines (psychology, natural science, sociology, etc.) and adapted to solving problems arising in the field of education or upbringing. The content of such pedagogy consists of fragmented ideas about individual aspects of pedagogical phenomena. About pedagogy, an independent discipline has its own educational object and subject.

The third point of view, according to which pedagogy is considered an independent scientific discipline, is the most recognized. Unlike everyday knowledge in the field of education and training, pedagogy as a science summarizes various facts and does not establish causal relationships.

It answers questions about what and why changes occur in human development under the influence of education and training.

To define pedagogy as a science, answering the question "What does it teach?" , it is important to define the boundaries of its topic. Therefore, it is necessary to understand the subject and the concept of pedagogy.

Object is the field of reality that science studies. The object of pedagogy is the life events that determine the development of human individuality in the purposeful process of community activity. Such a phenomenon of reality is a way of seeing the object from the point of view of the given science.

The subject of pedagogy is organized consciously and purposefully by process.

Under the understanding of the pedagogical process, which develops in a specially organized, timely and specific educational system, the interaction of teachers and students is aimed at achieving the goal of students, which leads to a change in personal goals qualities and characteristics.

The science of pedagogy studies the essence, laws, trends of principles and development prospects of the pedagogical process, develops the theory and technology of its organization, improves its content and creates new organizational forms, methods and techniques, educational activities teachers and students (children and adults).

Based on this understanding of the object and subject of pedagogy, we can come to the conclusion that pedagogy is education, teaching and learning for children and adults.

"Pedagogy derives its name from the Greek word ("pay-dagogos" "paid child gogos lead"), which means "child bearing" or child education ".

In Ancient Greece, this function was performed directly, the slaves who escorted their master's children to school were initially called teachers. Later, teachers were ordinary citizens who were involved in guiding, educating and teaching children. By the way, in Russia (XII century) the first teachers were called "masters". It was free people (clerks or laymen) who taught children to read, write, and pray at home or at home, as this "Life" says. Learn to write books and educate readers.

BOOKS:

1. Artykov N. National and universal human resources.
 2. Otamurodov S. Teacher of spirituality nfatasoslan-T 1991-2006
 3. Ochilov. M. Muallim qalbme mori - Teacher, 2001-429b
 4. Rizayev. O. History of Pedagogy-T "Cholpon", 1993
 5. Hasanboyevab "History of Pedagogy Tashkent 2004 page 4 nitsa: 4 iz 4
- Chislo slov: 533